

The new ECS SRIA: An Interview with Elisabeth Steimetz, ECS SRIA Chair.

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The Electronics Components and Systems (ECS) community just released the 2021 edition of its Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda - ECS SRIA. Patrick Cogez (AENEAS) and Patrick Pype (NXP) interviewed Elisabeth Steimetz, Office Director of EPoSS and Chair of the 2021 ECS SRIA.

Q: What is the purpose of the SRIA, and how is it elaborated?

The ECS SRIA is a collective document created by more than 300 experts from the ECS community serving multiple purposes. First of all, it sets the agenda for some of the significant European funding programmes for collaborative Research and Innovation projects in the area of ECS. It also provides priorities of research topics of our community for the next 15 years. We are combining technology push and application pull. We define roadmaps for foundational technology layers and consider the main application for areas of high interest for Europe by collecting their demands for ECS in the future.

Q: What is new in the 2021 edition?

Complementing the application-oriented sections and the foundational technology layers, we created so-called cross-sectional areas connecting the technologies layers and need to be addressed on all layers. One of these cross-sectional sections is on connectivity, which is of particular interest to the readers of this newsletter. Connectivity also appears across the whole document because of the requirements it generates towards foundational technologies and because many applications that we are targeting cannot be developed if we do not deploy 5G or 6G.

Another novelty is that we analyzed the significant R&I challenges identified in each of the individual sections and linked their contributions to four main European objectives:

- Boost industrial competitiveness through interdisciplinary technology innovations,
- Ensure EU strategic autonomy through secure, safe, and reliable ECS supporting key European application domains,
- Establish and strengthen sustainable and resilient ECS value chains supporting the Green Deal, and
- Unleash the full potential of intelligent and autonomous ECS-based systems for Europe's Digital Age.

This way, we were able to align our ambitions towards these shared objectives.

Q: The COREnect project develops a high-level strategic roadmap of core technologies for future connectivity systems and components and aims at providing the foundations for sustainable European technology sovereignty in 5G and beyond. How can the ECS SRIA contribute to that goal?

I think the ECS-SRIA can substantially contribute to the CoreNect roadmap activities and vice versa with almost a hundred percent synergy. Of course, the COREnect roadmap might look more into the details of the required technologies for connectivity systems and components, while the SRIA has a broader scope, but we are targeting the same topics. In the foundational technologies layers section, we addressed a couple of technologies where Europe is at the forefront and needs to be further developed and improved, such as RF Silicon On Insulator or BiCMOS technologies for terahertz applications. We are also stressing the importance of developing new miniaturized packaging technologies to go beyond the component level up to the module level, integrating antenna technologies and competencies in design. We would welcome experts from the COREnect team to contribute to the ECS SRIA.

In the new ECS SRIA, we have included the integrated photonics part. Experts believe that a merge of technologies will lay a fundamental basis for future developments in connectivity towards 6G. Your community's expertise will also be precious here to define these optical components' role and potential in future networks.

Sovereignty and autonomy aspects are one of the main objectives to which the ECS industry is contributing. Still, today we are not addressing all the individual details of developments across the connectivity value chain in Europe yet and have a strong dependency on China and the US for 5G technology. We should have a look at identifying gaps to establish value chains in Europe for 5 and 6G technology. Working together with the COREnect contributors on that point would definitely enrich our SRIA and could help to have Europe taking up leadership for 6G in a nutshell: we share your goals, and closer cooperation would be of benefit to both our communities.

Q: Do you see, beyond people from the COREnect community contributing to the SRIA, some other potential ways to build synergies or cross-fertilization between the two communities?

Yes, of course, what comes first to my mind are collaborative R&I projects, in particular with a focus on the industrialization of the technologies in Europe which we are developing. We have leading research institutions and companies in Europe working in the connectivity field. We master differentiating technologies like RFSOI, packaging, and design in massive MIMO, but this does not always lead to industrialisation in Europe. The ECS and SNS communities could establish an "Important Project of Common European Interest" (IPCEI) in the connectivity field and try to fill the gaps in the value chain. We have to bring these communities together and foster new companies' development to explore to create autonomy for crucial components and modules for Europe. In addition to such a large flagship project, we should also investigate opportunities for collaboration between the future SNS and KDT Public-Private Partnerships and the new EUREKA Cluster Programme across the current cluster communities.

Q: Any final words or key messages that you would like to get across?

I would like to welcome the COREnect project members to be part of the ECS SRIA team and have an in-depth exchange. We will be starting our annual updating process soon. We are very open and looking forward to the collaboration. I see, and I think that you agree, that connectivity is of utmost importance for European autonomy in the future and that we have to work together on that and really need to gain momentum.